

**REGARDING THE PHENOMENON OF WORD FORMATION
(On the example of English and Uzbek languages)**

*Z. Temirkhanova*¹

Abstract:

This article describes some approaches of word-formation on the example of English and Uzbek languages. Some similarities and differences are analyzed.

Key words: word-formation, semantic, phonetic, affixation, composition.

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Word formation is a pure speech phenomenon, a speech process. [4.144]. Word formation is one of the independent branches of linguistics (like lexicology and grammar), which studies the formation of new words, methods of word formation, and phenomena related to word formation in general.

Word formation in each language is based on the specific patterns of that language, i.e. on the basis of foreign words or internal possibilities. There are several ways of forming words in the Uzbek language:

1. Semantic;
2. Phonetic;
3. Syntactic-lexical;
4. Affixation;
5. Composition. [5.170]

Based on these, Professor Ayub Ghulomov notes the methods mentioned above, that is, in Uzbek language 1. Morphological formation (affixation) 2. Syntactic formation (reduplication, composition, abbreviation) 3. Lexical formation (forming by moving a word from one category to another category) 4. Semantic formation 5. Phonetic formation emphasizes the formation of a new word. [1.112].

We will consider them below: We have information about the emergence of homonyms as a result of the change and interruption of the connection between the meanings of a polysemous word. Creating a new word based on a change in the meaning of a word is called word formation by semantic method. For example: blue ("sky", noun) - blue ("color", adjective). [6.100] A new word is formed as a result of a change in the meaning of a word (word form) existing in the language in word formation using the semantic method: day (light part of the day) - day (sun, planet) [5.170].

There are also many words formed as a result of phonetic change (sound change) in the Uzbek language: blind-eye, chalk-gray. Word formation in this way is called phonetic word formation. [5.171]. In another literature, this method is presented as follows: the formation of a new word as a result of a change in the phonetic structure of a word is called phonetic word formation. For example: night and day, eye and blind, brother and brother. [6.100]

¹ Temirkhanova Zarina, student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Word formation by syntactic lexical method is understood as the transformation of a word combination into a word. Over time, certain types of word combinations can become one word. In this case, the word combination will express one meaning - the lexical meaning, and the syntactic connection between the components of the combination will disappear. As a result, the unit, which is actually a word combination, becomes a compound word. For example, compound words such as toqqaychi, kashkargul, mingboshi, khokhorpoya, elghtabiat, kaltafahm were formed in the same way. [5.171].

In addition, by adding an affix to a word, it is said to create a new word by the affixation method: worker, concrete worker, athlete, grower, open, closed, work, think, think, etc. [5.171]. One of the methods of word formation in the Uzbek language is the affixation method. This word formation method is created by adding suffixes to words. For example: gul-don, mountain, belt (moq). [7.45] This is also mentioned in other literature, in general, word formation by affixation is one of the most active methods in the Uzbek language. According to this method, new words are created by adding word-forming suffixes to the base. For example: writer, librarian. [1.112-113].

In the Uzbek language, in addition to creating a word by adding an affix, a new word is also created by adding more than one root (morpheme with an independent meaning). This method of word formation is called composition method. Compound words are made by the method of composition: ostrich, moon, rose, air color, buy, bring, never, always. [5.171]. Creating words in Uzbek by composition is a very productive way. A new word is formed by adding roots. For example: a bouquet, a shovel, a hand. [7.45]

Of course, the above-mentioned methods of word formation have been creating new words in the Uzbek language and enriching its vocabulary. If we look at the formation of words in English, there are several ways of forming words in this language:

In English, affixation is the creation of new words by adding suffixes to words. In the affixation method, a new word is created by adding affixes and suffixes to words: Dis+like dislike, ful+law lawful. [10.30]

Word cluster (synonymous words) - in English, such a word is formed using a semantically and phonetically similar group of words: heart, to disheart, to dishearten, disheartenment. [10.42].

In modern English, conversion is one of the most productive ways to create new words. In this case, a new word is created by changing a word from one word group to another word group. For example: a face-to face. [10.47]. Another literature states that Conversion is a method of word formation, in which a new word is created by changing the word group. This is as follows: home (n) - home (adv), down (prep) - down (v). [12.47]

Another way to create new words is by combining two or more words. Modern English is very rich in compound words. For example: railway, rainfall, easy-going, steamboat. This method of word formation is called the method of word formation through the event of composition. [13.144]

Abbreviations in English are similar to the Uzbek method of abbreviation, in which a new word is formed by writing the initial letters of words in a compound word or group of words. For example: BBC (British Broadcasting Corporation), USA (the United States of America).

In addition, there is a method of word formation by clipping in English, and this method of word formation is fundamentally different from the abbreviation method. Because in the abbreviation method only the first letter of the word is written, in this method the first syllable of the word, the middle of the word, the end of the word or in most cases the stressed syllable is written. For example: Sis. (sister), Jap (Japanese), Lab (laboratory), phone (telephone). [8.203]

In English, as in Uzbek, a new word is formed through the phenomenon of phonetic change (sound interchange). For example: food (n) –feed (v), speak (v) –speech (n), strong (adj) –strength(n). [J. Buranov, A. Muminov. A practical course in English lexicology] . in addition, if we turn to another literature, in which phonetic change (sound interchange) is formed through phonetic changes of word bases. For example: life n – live v, food n – feed v. [11.123]

Back-formation - the formation of words in this way in English is considered diachronic (historical). In this case, if we take the word speaker, this word is formed from the verb speak, and the noun speaker is formed as a result of adding the suffix er to the verb speak. We can cite many similar examples: to beg–beggar, to read–reader, to typewrite–typewriter [11.150].

Blending - word formation using this method is done by combining two independent words to form a new word. For example: "smoke" and "fog" sm (oke+g) fog=smog. [10.62]

Based on this, when we compare the ways of word formation in English and Uzbek languages, we can see that there are some differences between them. That is, they have different ways of forming words. However, word formation methods such as affixation, composition and abbreviation, conversion, phonetic change are very productive ways for both languages. But in Uzbek, word cluster, clipping, blending, and backformation are rarely used word formation methods. However, these methods are widely used in English. We can give very few examples of these ways of forming words in the Uzbek language.

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